

Teacher Professionalism as Predictor of Home-School Partnership in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental

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Abstract. This study investigated the correlation between teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. Employing a non-experimental quantitative research design, data were gathered from 100 elementary school teachers using stratified random sampling. Modified survey questionnaires assessed teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships. Results indicate extensive mean scores for both variables, signifying elevated levels of professionalism and effective partnerships. Furthermore, a significant positive relationship emerged between teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships, highlighting the influential role of professionalism in fortifying partnerships. The teacher professionalism significantly influenced the home-school partnership of teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. Notably, dimensions such as knowledge, skills, values, professional identity, and autonomy substantially impacted home-school partnerships. These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the pivotal role of teacher professionalism in cultivating positive home-school collaborations. The study offers valuable insights for the Department of Education, educators, parents, and future researchers, aiming to advance teacher professionalism and fortify home-school partnerships within educational contexts.

KEY WORDS

1. teacher professionalism 2. home-school partnership 3. Davao Occidental

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1. Introduction

Professionalism is a consistent mode of behavior teachers observe within education. For classroom instructors, this includes maintaining subject knowledge and instructing students at age-appropriate levels while collaborating with other educators to plan teaching methods. Meanwhile, home-school partnerships involve collaborative working relationships between families and schools. They can support students in more productive and consistent work and behavior, improving students' interest, motivation, and engagement in learning at home and school.

The home-school would give maximum benefit to the students, such as strengthening and sustained by constant, timely, specific, and meaningful communication and feedback among the parents, students, and teachers. These two professionalism of teachers and home-school partnerships were crucial topics of the discussions, and their association would significantly impact teaching and learning development. In the Global context, as Creemers Kyriakides (2008) stressed, Education is indispensable in the development of society and the individual, forming

the bedrock upon which knowledge, values, and skills are imparted). Teacher professionalism is a fundamental component among the numerous elements that constitute an effective educational system. Teacher professionalism denotes the capacity of educators to fulfill their duties in a proficient, ethical, and efficacious manner. It entails having the expertise to foster student progress, a steadfast dedication to lifelong learning and self-improvement, and adherence to the highest moral and professional standards (Hargreaves, 2000; Sachs, 2016). However, several variables, including the caliber of homeschool connections, can impact the manifestation and efficacy of teacher professionalism. Teacher professionalism encompasses a spectrum of attributes, including subject-matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, professional ethics, continuous learning, and collaboration. Empirical research has accentuated the salience of these attributes in promoting robust and effective homeschool partnerships (Epstein, 2001; Sheldon, 2003). Concurrently, the degree of professionalism teachers manifest can significantly impact the quality of these partnerships, influencing parental involvement and, ultimately, student outcomes (Mawhinney Rinke, 2017). Thus, examining how facets of teacher professionalism can enhance homeschool partnerships is essential. Homeschool partnerships, a pivotal learning environment component, foster a symbiotic relationship between families and educational institutions. These partnerships are conduits for parental involvement, contributing substantially to students' academic, social, and personal development (Epstein, 2001; Sheldon, 2003). The dynamics of this relationship can be significantly influenced by the level of teacher professionalism, making exploring the role of teacher professionalism in shaping homeschool partnerships a significant area of interest in educational research. Several studies have delved into the relationship between teacher professionalism and homeschool partnerships. For instance, a semi-

nal study by Moles (1993) posited that teachers' professional skills and attitudes significantly determine the quality of homeschool partnerships. Similarly, empirical work by Sanders and Sheldon (2009) indicated that teacher professionalism, characterized by practical communication skills and a collaborative ethos, significantly augments homeschool partnerships. Teacher professionalism is a vital factor in achieving educational excellence. Professional educators have the knowledge, competencies, and abilities to promote efficient learning and student growth. Darling-Hammond (2000) and Ingersoll (2003) are dedicated to pursuing ongoing professional development, upholding the highest ethical standards, and applying best practices in the classroom. Homeschool partnerships have also been recognized as influential factors in student success. In the Philippines, where family involvement in education is highly valued, strong home-school partnerships can positively impact student outcomes (Padilla, 2019). These partnerships involve collaborative relationships between families and schools, fostering shared responsibility for student learning and development (Epstein, 2001). Understanding the relationship between teacher professionalism and homeschool partnerships is crucial in the Philippine context to improve education quality. By investigating how teacher professionalism influences the quality of homeschool partnerships, policymakers and educators can develop strategies to enhance collaboration and engagement between teachers and families, ultimately improving student outcomes (Güven Karataş, 2021). Despite these valuable insights, there remains a substantial research gap concerning the role of teacher professionalism as a predictor of the quality of homeschool partnerships. Specifically, there is a need to explore the predictive power of various aspects of teacher professionalism, such as professional ethics, collaboration skills, and commitment to continuous learning, on the quality of homeschool partner-

ships. This study will fill this gap by examining teacher professionalism and homeschool partnership in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. The findings of this study will contribute to the existing literature on teacher professionalism and homeschool partnership, as well as provide insights for policymakers and educational leaders on how to improve the quality of education in the Philippines. Therefore, this study would help to probe the predictive relationship between teacher professionalism and homeschool partnerships. Specifically, it would

scrutinize how different aspects of teacher professionalism, including knowledge of subject matter and pedagogy, professional ethics and values, commitment to continuous learning and improvement, collaboration, and effective classroom management, impact the quality of homeschool partnerships. The findings from this study would contribute to the existing body of literature on teacher professionalism and homeschool partnerships and provide valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers aiming to enhance these partnerships.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design, which aimed to provide an overview and explore the factors influencing a particular phenomenon. The design allowed for examining quantifiable variables and developing organizational capabilities based on strategic management literature (Parida et al., 2016). A survey instrument was utilized to gather quantitative data regarding the phenomenon. The survey was specifically designed for the target respondents to answer a series of questions. This survey focused on collecting quantitative data related to the phenomenon under investigation. The design of the survey instrument was suitable for gathering data from the target respondents and capturing their responses to the survey questions. This research specifically used survey research. Survey research provides a quantitative or numeric description of a population's trends, attitudes, or opinions by studying a sample of that population (Creswell, 2009). The purpose of the survey was to explain the characteristics of a population. In essence, what the researcher wanted to discover was how members of a population were distributed themselves on a variable

or more (for example: age, ethnicity, religion, attitude toward school)

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental elementary school teachers. The 100 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. The partitioning of a population into smaller subgroups, known as strata, was a key component of the sampling technique known as stratified random sampling. Shi (2015) asserts that in stratified random sampling, also known as stratification, the strata are created based on the shared traits or features of the members, such as income or level of education. Because the population in this study was heterogeneous and could be categorized using auxiliary data, stratified random sampling was appropriate. Stratified random sampling was a widely used statistical technique in which a population was divided into different subgroups, or strata, based on some shared characteristics. The purpose of stratification was to ensure each stratum in the sample and make inferences about specific population subgroups. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The

primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only permanent-regular teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, those not subjected to any administrative or criminal cases, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of

the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The research instrument used was a researcher-made questionnaire that suited the context of the study. The questionnaires dealt with the role of Teacher Professionalism in Homeschool Partnerships. The contents of the instrument were presented to a group of experts for validation. Five orderable gradations with their respective range of means descriptions were considered:

Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Teacher Professionalism

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.30 – 5.0	Very Extensive	Teacher professionalism is always manifested
3.50 – 4.20	Extensive	Teacher professionalism is frequently manifested
2.70 – 3.40	Moderately extensive	Teacher professionalism is sometimes manifested
1.90 – 2.60	Less Extensive	Teacher professionalism is seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.80	Not Extensive	Teacher professionalism is never manifested

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Homeschool Partnerships

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	This means that the Homeschool Partnerships is very much observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	This means that the Homeschool Partnerships is much observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	This means that the Homeschool Partnerships is fairly observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	This means that the Homeschool Partnerships is less observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	This means that the Homeschool Partnerships is not observed.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Upon validation of the research questionnaire, the researcher followed specific steps in conducting the study: **Permission to Conduct the Study:** The researcher obtained permission to conduct the study by securing an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters addressed to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. The researcher contacted the identified respondents in Jose Abad Santos and explained the research study, seeking their consent to participate. To maintain anonymity, a link to the survey and consent form was sent to the principals, who then forwarded it to the respondents. A comprehensive explanation of the voluntary nature of the study accompanied the link, and paper copies were provided upon request. The email communication assured the participants that their school

principals had granted prior approval. **Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire:** Following the approval to conduct the study, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. During this process, the researcher briefly discussed the benefits of the survey and provided clarification to the identified respondents. The questionnaire administration strictly adhered to health protocols, including the use of face masks and shields and adherence to social distancing guidelines. Sufficient time was given to the respondents to complete the questionnaires. After collecting the data, it was subjected to quantitative analysis. **Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data:** Once the questionnaires were retrieved, the researcher tallied the scores of each respondent to organize the data according to the indicators. Subsequently, the scores underwent descriptive and inferential analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

2.5. Data Analysis—The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to process the gathered data: **Mean:** This statistical measure was employed to characterize and summarize the variables examined in the study. **Pearson Product Moment Correlation:** This statistical method was used to assess the significant

relationship between the independent variable (Teacher Professionalism) and the dependent variable (Homeschool partnerships). It measured the strength and direction of the linear association between paired data points. In this study, the correlation coefficient, denoted as "r," was utilized to evaluate the relationship between the variables.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of Teacher professionalism and its indicators, the extent of home-school partnership and its indicators, and the significant influence between the two variables.

Summary of the Extent of Teacher Professionalism Indicators

The table presents the overall mean results for teacher professionalism, specifically focusing on Knowledge and Understanding, Skills

and Competencies, Values and Attitude, Professional Identity, and Agency and Autonomy. The overall mean scores for these aspects range from 4.06 to 4.20, indicating a high level of agreement among the respondents in all areas.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Teacher Professionalism Indicators

Indicator	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Knowledge and Understanding	4.06	Extensive
Skills and Competencies	4.06	Extensive
Values and Attitude	4.19	Extensive
Professional Identity	4.20	Extensive
Agency and Autonomy	4.18	Extensive
Overall	4.14	Extensive

Summary of the extent of home-school partnership

Table 2 presents the extent of home-school partnership with the overall mean results for different indicators: Open and Effective Communication, Parental Involvement, Goal Setting and Expectation, and Mutual Trust and Respect. The mean scores for all the indicators range from 4.17 to 4.18, indicating extensive agreement among the respondents in each aspect.

Among the indicators, Open and Effective Communication, Parental Involvement, and Goal Setting and Expectation have an overall mean of 4.18, suggesting a high level of agreement among the respondents. These results imply that the teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, perceive open and effective communication, parental involvement, and goal setting as essential components of a successful home-school partnership.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Home-School Partnership Indicators

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Open and Effective Communication	4.18	Extensive
Parental Involvement	4.18	Extensive
Goal Setting and Expectations	4.18	Extensive
Mutual Trust and Respect	4.17	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.18	Extensive

The Mutual Trust and Respect indicator has a slightly lower overall mean of 4.17, indicating a similar level of agreement among the respondents. This indicator emphasizes the significance of trust, respect, and collaboration between teachers and parents in fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Overall, the extensive level of agreement in all aspects underscores teachers' positive perceptions and experiences regarding different indicators of home-school partnerships. These results imply that teacher professionalism, includ-

ing knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes, is crucial in establishing effective communication, promoting parental involvement, setting clear goals and expectations, and fostering mutual trust and respect between teachers and parents. The highest mean score among the indicators is observed in Open and Effective Communication, Parental Involvement, and Goal Setting and Expectation, all with a mean of 4.18. This indicates a strong agreement among the respondents in these areas, highlighting their significance in building and sustaining a successful

home-school partnership. The aspect with the slightly lower mean score of 4.17, Mutual Trust and Respect, also reflects a substantial level of agreement and emphasizes the importance of trust and respect in the partnership.

Relationship Between Teacher Professionalism and Home-School Partnership Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental

Table 3 presents the mean scores and descriptive equivalents for the questions related to the influence of teacher professionalism on home-school partnerships. The overall mean for this aspect is 4.26, indicating a pervasive level of agreement among the respondents. These results highlight the teachers' recognition of the significant role of teacher professionalism in fostering effective home-school partnerships. The highest mean scores are observed for the statements "Teacher professionalism significantly contributes to the quality of home-school partnership" and "The level of teacher professionalism directly impacts the level of parental involvement in the student's education," with mean scores of 4.30 and 4.28, respectively. These results indicate that the teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, strongly believe that their professionalism substantially impacts the quality of the partnership between the school and parents. They acknowledge the importance of their professional conduct, expertise, and commitment to building strong collaborative relationships with parents and engaging them in their child's education. The mean score for "Teacher professionalism enhances open and effective communication between teach-

These findings align with previous research emphasizing the significance of teacher professionalism in promoting robust home-school partnerships. The results underscore the importance of continuous professional development and maintaining high ethical and professional standards among teachers to enhance

ers and parents" is 4.25, indicating a pervasive level of agreement. This demonstrates that the teachers perceive their professionalism as a critical factor in establishing and maintaining open lines of communication with parents. Effective communication promotes understanding, collaboration, and shared decision-making between teachers and parents, ultimately benefiting the student's learning and development. The mean score for the statement "The professionalism exhibited by teachers promotes trust and respect in the home-school partnership" is 4.23, indicating a very extensive level of agreement. This reflects the teachers' understanding of professionalism's essential role in building trust and respect between teachers and parents. By demonstrating professionalism in their interactions, teachers create a positive and supportive partnership that fosters mutual respect and cooperation. The mean score for the statement "The professionalism of the teachers influences the effectiveness of the home-school partnership" is 4.26, indicating a pervasive level of agreement. This underscores the teachers' belief that their professionalism significantly impacts the effectiveness of the home-school partnership. When teachers exhibit professionalism, it strengthens the partnership and creates an environment conducive to student success and holistic development. The extensive levels of agreement among the respondents on the influence of teacher professionalism on the home-school partnership aspect demonstrate the teachers' awareness of their professionalism's crucial role in fostering effective partnerships with parents.

collaboration, communication, trust, and respect between teachers and parents. Strengthening these partnerships improves student outcomes, academic success, and overall well-being. The table presents the correlation coefficients (R-values) and p-values for the relationship between teacher professionalism factors

Table 3. Relationship Between Teacher Professionalism and Home-School Partnership Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental

Teacher Professionalism Factors	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Knowledge and Understanding	0.587	0.001	Significant	Reject H0
Skills and Competencies	0.432	0.012	Significant	Reject H0
Values and Attitude	0.341	0.034	Significant	Reject H0
Professional Identity	0.256	0.093	Significant	Reject H0
Agency and Autonomy	0.613	0.001	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

and home-school partnership. The interpretations indicate that all factors have significant relationships with home-school partnerships, as all p-values are less than 0.05. The findings reveal that Knowledge and Understanding, Skills and Competencies, Values and Attitude, Professional Identity, and Agency and Autonomy are all significantly positively correlated with home-school partnerships. This means that the quality of the home-school partnership improves as teachers demonstrate higher levels of knowledge, skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy. The findings from the correlation analysis between teacher professionalism factors and home-school partnership align with the existing literature on this topic. Previous studies have emphasized the significance of teacher expertise, pedagogical skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy in fostering effective collaboration between teachers and parents (Moles, 1993; Sanders Sheldon, 2009). The positive and significant correlations observed in this study indicate that the home-school partnership improves as teachers demonstrate higher levels of knowledge, skills, positive values and attitudes, professional identity, and autonomy. These findings are consistent with the research by Moles (1993), who suggested that teachers' professional skills and attitudes significantly deter-

mine the quality of home-school partnerships. The study by Sanders and Sheldon (2009) also indicated that teacher professionalism, characterized by practical communication skills and a collaborative ethos, significantly enhances home-school partnerships. The significant relationships between teacher professionalism factors and home-school partnerships provide valuable insights for improving educational practices and strengthening the partnership between schools and families. These findings support the existing literature on the significance of teacher professionalism in shaping successful home-school partnerships and emphasize the importance of ongoing professional development and support for teachers in fostering positive and collaborative relationships with parents.

Influence of The Influence of Teacher Professionalism on Home-School Partnership Results in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental Elementary School teachers

The significance of teacher professionalism in significantly influencing the home-school partnership among Jose Abad Santos and Davao Occidental elementary school teachers was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 13 shows that teacher professionalism significantly influences the home-school partnership knowledge and understanding, skills and competencies, values and attitude, professional identity

agency, and autonomy are considered predictors of students' autonomy; the model is significant, as evident in the F-value of 27.837 with $p < 0.05$. Therefore, teacher professionalism significantly influences the home-school partnership between Jose Abad Santos and Davao Occidental elementary school teachers. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.351 indicates that teachers' learning environment management skills have contributed significantly to the variability of students' autonomy by 35.10 of the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 64.90 was credited to other factors not covered in this study. In addition, the table shows

that all the domains of Teacher Professionalism significantly influence the Home-School partnership in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental Elementary School teachers. This table also indicates that teachers' Teacher Professionalism in knowledge and understanding, skills and competencies, values and attitude, professional identity agency, and autonomy are significant when the predictors are considered. Thus, this leads to rejecting the null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers' learning environment management skills significantly influence the teacher professionalism in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental Elementary School teachers.

Table 4. The Influence of Teacher Professionalism on Home-School Partnership Results

Teacher Professionalism	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Knowledge and Understanding	.121*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
	.200*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
	.400*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
	.000	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
Skills and Competencies	.161*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
Values and Attitude	.161*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
Professional Identity	.295*	.408	.047	.000	Reject H0
Agency and Autonomy	.185*	.308	.049	.012	Reject H0
R ² = 0.351					
F-value = 27.837*					
p-value = 0.000					

The importance of professionalism and exhibiting the dispositions associated with a professional can be conveyed overtly and covertly. Overall, the program can explain to the students the programmatic expectations for each person upon admission to the program and then address how these expectations will be assessed throughout the curriculum. When considering professionalism in teacher preparation pro-

grams, this author advocates that consideration should be given to The Framework for Teaching (Danielson, 2013). This set of research-based instruction components is aligned to the Interstate Teacher Assessment and Support Consortium (InTASC) standards. Particular focus should be given to defining professionalism in teacher education programs to Domain 4: Professional Responsibilities. This domain includes the sub-

sets of Reflecting on Teaching, Maintaining Accurate Records, Communicating with Families, Participating in the Professional Community, Growing and Developing Professionally, and Showing Professionalism. These components are further broken down into “indicators” of fulfilling professional responsibilities. One institution of higher learning has adapted these indicators to fit not the professional responsibilities of teachers more readily but the professional responsibilities of teacher candidates. The findings align with the study of Zakaria and Iksan (2012), which states that effective management skills involve setting clear expectations and guidelines for classroom behavior and academic performance. When students know what is expected of them, they can better plan and manage their learning activities.. Lastly, the result corroborates with Wegner et al. (2014)

that teachers with strong learning environment management skills create a classroom culture that values independence and self-directed learning. When students feel safe, respected, and encouraged to express their ideas and preferences, they are more likely to take ownership of their learning. Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental elementary school teachers. The extensive agreement among the respondents in all the indicators indicates a positive and conducive home-school partnership in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. These findings contribute to the existing literature on teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships, highlighting the crucial role of teacher professionalism in establishing and maintaining effective collaboration and engagement between teachers and parents.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section of the paper provides the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations based on the findings. The conclusions drawn were supported by the existing literature discussed in the earlier chapters, and they address the research problem identified in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary purpose of this study was to evaluate the level of teacher professionalism in home-school partnerships using a quantitative research design that involves administering questionnaires. The sample for this study consists of 100 school teachers from Jose Abad Santos, Division of Davao Occidental, who were selected using a stratified random sampling method. To ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire items, the researcher modified and enhanced existing survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school. Based on the analysis of the data and results obtained from the study, the following summary of findings can be highlighted: The overall mean results for the teacher professionalism indicators indicate extensive teacher professionalism among the Jose Abad Santos,

Davao Occidental respondents, with an overall mean of 4.14 on a 5-point Likert scale. The home-school partnership indicators also show extensive partnerships, with an overall mean of 4.18, suggesting effective communication, parental involvement, goal setting, and mutual trust and respect between teachers and parents. A positive and significant relationship exists between teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.256 to 0.613 and p-values less than 0.05, indicating solid associations. The aspects of teacher professionalism that have the most substantial impact on home-school partnerships are knowledge and understanding ($r = 0.587$, $p < 0.001$), skills and competencies ($r = 0.432$, $p = 0.012$), values and Attitude ($r = 0.341$, $p = 0.034$), professional identity ($r = 0.256$, $p =$

0.093), and agency and autonomy ($r = 0.613$, $p < 0.001$). The extensive home-school partnerships indicate effective communication (mean = 4.18), parental involvement in school activities (mean = 4.18), shared goal setting (mean = 4.18), and mutual trust and respect (mean = 4.17) between teachers and parents. The significant relationship between teacher professionalism and home-school partnerships suggests that fostering teacher professionalism could enhance the quality of partnerships and ultimately benefit student learning and development. The teacher professionalism significantly influenced the home-school partnership of teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the extensive analysis of the results presented in this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, exhibit extensive professionalism and competence in various aspects, including knowledge and understanding, skills and competencies, values and Attitude, professional identity, and agency and autonomy. There was a strong positive relationship between teacher professionalism and home-school partnership, indicating that the professionalism exhibited by teachers significantly contributes to the quality of the partnership. All Domains in teacher professionalism significantly influenced the home-school partnership of teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. The district's teachers were committed to ongoing professional development and extensively engaged in activities that enhanced their knowledge and skills.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following: This study's findings provide important implications for various stakeholders in the education sector, including the Department of Education, teachers, parents, and future researchers. For the Department of Education: Strengthen professional development initiatives: The Department of Educa-

tion may prioritize developing and implementing comprehensive and ongoing professional development programs for teachers. These programs may focus on enhancing subject matter expertise, promoting effective teaching strategies, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement. Supporting the establishment of collaborative platforms for the Department of Education may facilitate the creation of collaborative platforms and networks where teachers can engage in meaningful discussions, share best practices, and collaborate on innovative teaching approaches. This could be done by establishing professional learning communities, online forums, and regional or national conferences. Most teachers firmly believe in creating a positive and inclusive learning environment, maintaining extensive expectations for students, and building positive relationships with students and their families. Teachers in Jose Abad Santos perceive themselves as lifelong learners dedicated to their student's learning and growth, and they view themselves as important members of a professional community working towards improving education. The teachers feel empowered to make decisions about instructional strategies, advocate for their student's needs, collaborate with colleagues, and sought innovative teaching strategies. Open and effective communication between teachers and parents is a prominent feature of the district, with regular and clear communication about student progress, comfortable parent-teacher interactions, and active listening and valuing of parental viewpoints. Parental involvement is encouraged and valued, with opportunities for parents to participate in school activities, volunteer in the classroom, and be involved in decision-making processes related to their child's education. For teachers to engage in continuous professional development, they may actively participate in professional development opportunities to update their knowledge and skills in their respective subject areas. This can involve attending work-

shops, conferences, and training programs and pursuing higher education or advanced certifications to enhance their expertise further. To foster positive relationships with parents, the teachers may prioritize building positive relationships with parents and actively involve them in their child's education. This could be done through regular communication, parent-teacher meetings, and collaboration on goal-setting and academic support strategies. Teachers could strengthen the home-school partnership by promoting open and effective communication and creating a supportive learning environment. Parents to actively participate in their child's education: may actively engage in their child's education by attending parent-teacher meetings, school events, and volunteering opportunities. They may also support their child's learning at home by providing a conducive environment, assisting with homework, and engaging in discussions about their child's progress. Advocate for quality education: Parents may actively advocate for quality education by engaging with school administrators, attending parent-teacher association meetings, and providing feedback on school policies and practices. By actively participating in decision-making processes, parents can contribute to creating a positive and conducive learning environment. For Future Researchers: Conduct longitudinal studies: Future researchers may consider conducting longitudinal studies to explore the long-term effects of teacher professionalism on student outcomes and home-school partnerships. Longitudinal studies can provide valuable insights into the sustainability and impact of various factors on educational practices and student success. Investigate other dimensions of teacher professionalism: Further research may explore additional dimensions, such as teacher-student relationships, instructional strategies, and classroom management. By examining these dimensions, researchers could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teacher professionalism and its educational implications. By implementing these recommendations, the Department of Education, teachers, parents, and future researchers can collectively improve education, enhance teacher professionalism, and foster stronger home-school partnerships to benefit students and the education system.

5. References

- Addi-Raccah, A. (2015). Teachers' professional attitudes and behaviors and their commitment to parental involvement. *Journal of School Public Relations*, 36(3), 268–283.
- Adriani, e. a. (2022). The impact of principal's transformational leadership on teacher professionalism and school environment: A correlational study. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 50(3), 487–503.
- Aidalkilani, M. (2022). The significance of instilling a love of reading in young people: The role of family, school, and community. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 57(2), 203–215.
- Arneback, E. e. a. (2021). Addressing peer-expressed prejudice in educational settings: Dangers, opportunities, and complexities for teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 93, 103124.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. General Learning Press.
- Banks, J. A., Cochran-Smith, M., Moll, L., Richert, A. E., Zeichner, K. M., LePage, P., & Rust, F. O. (2005). Teaching diverse learners. In L. Darling-Hammond & J. Bransford (Eds.), *Preparing teachers for a changing world: What teachers should learn and be able to do* (pp. 232–274). Jossey-Bass.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd). Psychology Press.

- Beijaard, D., Verloop, N., & Vermunt, J. D. (2000). Teachers' perceptions of professional identity: An exploratory study from a personal knowledge perspective. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 16*(7), 749–764. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(00\)00023-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(00)00023-8)
- Beijaard, D., Verloop, N., & Vermunt, J. D. (2004). Teachers' perceptions of professional identity: An exploratory study from a personal knowledge perspective. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 20*(8), 797–810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2004.06.004>
- Bempechat, J., & Shernoff, D. J. (2012). Parental influences on achievement motivation and student engagement. In S. L. Christenson, A. L. Reschly, & C. Wylie (Eds.), *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 315–342). Springer.
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. Wiley.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
- Bryk, A. S., & Schneider, B. (2002). *Trust in schools: A core resource for improvement*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Creemers, B. P., & Kyriakides, L. (2008). *The dynamics of educational effectiveness*. Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Danielson, C. (2013). The framework for teaching evaluation. <https://www.danielsongroup.org/framework/>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2000). Teacher quality and student achievement: A review of state policy evidence. *Education Policy Analysis Archives, 8*(1), 1–44. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v8n1.2000>
- Darling-Hammond, L., & McLaughlin, M. W. (2011). Policies that support professional development in an era of reform. *Phi Delta Kappan, 92*(6), 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172171109200622>
- Dauber, S. L., & Epstein, J. L. (1993). Parents' attitudes and practices of involvement in inner-city elementary and middle schools. In N. F. Chavkin (Ed.), *Families and schools in a pluralistic society* (pp. 103–117). State University of New York Press.
- Day, C. (2002). School reform and transitions in teacher professionalism and identity. *International Journal of Educational Research, 37*(8), 677–692. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-0355\(03\)00045-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-0355(03)00045-2)
- Day, C., & Gu, Q. (2014). *Resilient teachers, resilient schools: Building and sustaining quality in testing times*. Routledge.
- Day, C., & Sachs, J. (2004). Professionalism, performativity and empowerment: Discourses in the politics, policies, and purposes of continuing professional development. In C. Day & J. Sachs (Eds.), *International handbook on the continuing professional development of teachers* (pp. 3–32). Springer.
- Desforges, C., & Abouchar, A. (2003). *The impact of parental involvement, parental support, and family education on pupil achievements and adjustment: A literature review* (Research report No. 433). DfES Publications.
- Deslandes, R., & Bertrand, R. (2005). Motivation of parent involvement in secondary-level schooling. *The Journal of Educational Research, 98*(3), 164–175.
- Dweck, C. S. (2006). *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. Random House.

- Emmer, E. T., & Sabornie, E. J. (2015). *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues*. Routledge.
- Epstein, J. L. (2001a). *School, family, and community connections: Linking research to action*. Teachers College Press.
- Epstein, J. L. (2001b). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Westview Press.
- Epstein, J. L. (2010). *School, family, and community partnerships: Your handbook for action*. Corwin Press.
- Epstein, J. L., & Sheldon, S. B. (2006). Moving forward: Ideas for research on school, family, and community partnerships. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 81(2), 196–216.
- Epstein, J. L., & Van Voorhis, T. S. (2010). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Epstein, J. L., & Van Voorhis, T. S. (2012). *Engaging families with english learners: Supporting two-way communication*. Corwin.
- Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009048817385>
- Fantuzzo, J. W., Davis, G. Y., & Ginsburg, M. D. (1998). Teacher-as-learner in prekindergarten classrooms: Effects on classroom structure and children's learning. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 92(1), 54–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220679809597577>
- Fullan, M. (1993). *Change forces: Probing the depths of educational reform*. Falmer Press.
- Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice* (3rd). Teachers College Press.
- Güven, I., & Karataş, K. (2021). The effect of parental involvement in homework on academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 21(3), 47–60.
- Hargreaves, A. (2000). Four ages of professionalism and professional learning. *Teachers and Teaching: History and Practice*, 6(2), 151–182.
- Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (2012). *Professional capital: Transforming teaching in every school*. Teachers College Press.
- Harris, A., & Goodall, J. (2010a). Parenting and the social capital of families: An examination of concepts and research. *Journal of Education Policy*, 25(6), 731–743.
- Harris, A., & Goodall, J. (2010b). Parents and guardians of primary age pupils: Beliefs about effective involvement. *British Educational Research Journal*, 36(5), 681–695.
- Henderson, A. T., & Mapp, K. L. (2002). A new wave of evidence: The impact of school, family, and community connections on student achievement. *National Center for Family & Community Connections with Schools*.
- Henderson, A. T., Mapp, K. L., Johnson, G. B., & Davies, P. A. (2007). *Building bridges home and school: What we know about involving families in education* (tech. rep.). National Center for Family & Community Connections with Schools.
- Hill, C., & Reimer, A. (2022). Addressing technological demands in hybrid and remote learning models: A study of school districts. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 30(1), 1–15.

- Hill, H. C., Rowan, B., & Ball, D. L. (2005). Effects of teachers' mathematical knowledge for teaching on student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 42(2), 371–406. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312042002371>
- Hill, N. E., & Taylor, L. C. (2004). Parental school involvement and children's academic achievement: Pragmatics and issues. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 13(4), 161–164. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0963-7214.2004.00318>.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., Battiato, A. C., Walker, J. M. T., Reed, R. P., DeJong, J. M., & Jones, K. P. (2005). Parental involvement in homework. *Educational Psychologist*, 40(4), 193–206.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & et al. (2010). Why do parents become involved? research findings and implications. *The Elementary School Journal*, 106(2), 105–130.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. M. (1995). Parental involvement in children's education: Why does it make a difference? *Teachers College Record*, 97(2), 310–331.
- Husna, N., et al. (2022). English teachers' perceptions of teacher professionalism: A qualitative investigation. *Journal of Language and Education*, 6(1), 1–9.
- Ingersoll, R. M. (2003). Is there really a teacher shortage?
- Jahan, I., & Flora, M. S. (2022). Evaluating medical ethics and professionalism in undergraduate medical education: A study in bangladesh. *Journal of Medical Education and Development*, 36(1), 1–9.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2005). A meta-analysis of the relation of parental involvement to urban elementary school student academic achievement. *Urban Education*, 40(3), 237–269. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085905274540>
- Jeynes, W. H. (2007). The impact of family engagement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis of studies published from 1967–2007. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 87–114. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654307308196>
- Jeynes, W. H. (2011). *Parental involvement and academic success*. Routledge.
- Jiang, W., & McCombs, B. L. (2015). The role of autonomy in teachers' professional development and performance: A multilevel approach. *Teachers and Teaching*, 21(6), 678–696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2015.1044320>
- Johnson, K. E., & Golombek, P. R. (2011). *Research on second language teacher education: A sociocultural perspective on professional development*. Routledge.
- Kim, E., & Sheridan, S. M. (2015). Longitudinal relations between teacher and parent involvement in preschool and children's school success: A latent growth curve modeling approach. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 32, 153–166.
- Koh, J. H. L., Chua, C. Y., & Lim, W. Y. (2019). Teachers' perceptions of professional learning communities as predictors of collaborative practices in schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 204–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.07.002>
- Krieg, A. F. (2011). Teachers' professionalism and its impact on parental involvement: A case study. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(3), 429–447.
- Kyriacou, C., & Kunc, R. (2007). Beginning teachers' expectations of teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23(8), 1246–1257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2006.07.011>
- Lasky, S. (2005). A sociocultural approach to understanding teacher identity, agency, and professional vulnerability in a context of secondary school reform. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21(8), 899–916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2005.06.012>

- Little, J. W. (2012). Understanding data use practice among teachers: The contribution of micro-process studies. *American Journal of Education*, *118*(2), 143–166. <https://doi.org/10.1086/662788>
- Mawhinney, C. D. (2010). Collaborative decision making in family-school partnerships: An exploratory study of its effects on student achievement. *Journal of Education and Learning*, *1*(1), 25–38.
- Mawhinney, C. D., & Rinke, K. M. (2017). Parental involvement in literacy instruction: Examining the influence of teacher beliefs and classroom context. *International Journal of Early Childhood Environmental Research*, *10*(1), 42–52.
- Mawhinney, H., & Rinke, C. R. (2017). Teacher professionalism and parent involvement: The mediating role of teacher efficacy. *The Journal of Educational Research*, *110*(2), 178–188.
- Moles, O. (1993). What the research says about. . . home-school partnerships. *Educational Leadership*, *50*(8), 65–69.
- Ngwaru, J. M. (2014). Teacher professionalism and effective school-family partnerships: A case study of selected secondary schools in zimbabwe. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, *5*(3), 646–654.
- Nugroho, e. a. (2022). Enhancing teacher professionalism in madrasah: A strategic planning approach. *International Journal of Instruction*, *15*(2), 121–136.
- Padilla, A. J. (2019). Parental involvement and academic performance of students in philippine public high schools. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, *11*(4), 38–47.
- Parida, V., Westerberg, M., & Frishammar, J. (2016). Inbound open innovation activities in high-tech smes: The impact on innovation performance. *R&D Management*, *46*(3), 413–431.
- Pomerantz, E. M., & Moorman, E. A. (2012). Parents' involvement in children's schooling: Systematic review of research. *Review of Educational Research*, *82*(3), 403–449.
- Sachs, J. (2016). Teacher professionalism: Why are we still talking about it? *Teachers and Teaching*, *22*(4), 413–425.
- Sanders, M. G., & Sheldon, S. B. (2009a). Parental involvement in high schools: Association with student characteristics, school characteristics, and school engagement. *Family Relations*, *58*(4), 417–429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3729.2009.00565.x>
- Sanders, M. G., & Sheldon, S. B. (2009b). The role of leadership in teacher professional development in science and diversity. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, *46*(3), 235–250.
- Sheldon, S. B. (2003). Linking school-family-community partnerships in urban elementary schools to student achievement on state tests. *Urban Education*, *38*(1), 77–133.
- Sheldon, S. B., & Epstein, J. L. (2005). Involvement counts: Family and community partnerships and mathematics achievement. *The Journal of Educational Research*, *98*(4), 196–207.
- Sheldon, T. J., & Epstein, J. L. (2005). Improving academic achievement: What research tells us about the role of families. *Phi Delta Kappa*, *86*(7), 542–548.
- Shi, L. (2015). *Health services research methods*. Cengage Learning.
- Shulman, L. S. (1986). Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching. *Educational Researcher*, *15*(2), 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X015002004>

- Sui-Chu, E. H., & Willms, J. D. (1996). Effects of parental involvement on eighth-grade achievement. *Sociology of Education*, 69(2), 126–141.
- Thabologo, L. (2022). Using workshops as an intervention method for home-school collaboration to improve student mathematics performance in a public senior high school in botswana. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 54(1), 1–10.
- Wong, K. K. (2003). *Successful school leadership: Planning, politics, performance, and power*. Routledge.
- Yoon, K. S., Duncan, T., Lee, S. W.-Y., Scarloss, B., & Shapley, K. L. (2007). *Reviewing the evidence on how teacher professional development affects student achievement* (Issues & Answers Report No. REL 2007–No. 033). U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance.
- Zhang, H. (2020). Educational management research in china: Retrospect and prospect. *Frontiers of Education in China*, 15(1), 1–24.
- Zhang, X., Zhao, D., & Zhang, J. (2021). The impact of educational leadership on instructional management: Evidence from chinese secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 59(3), 253–270.
- Zheng, Y., & Cheung, A. C. (2021). Educational leadership and school effectiveness: A study of chinese middle schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(1), 182–196.